

Action of Lewis Acids on Aromatic Acetals

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Acetals of the type $X.C_6H_4.CH(OR)_2$, where $R = Et, n-Bu$ and isoamyl, and $X = H$ and CH_3 , react with antimony pentachloride and ferric chloride in anhydrous 1,2-dichloroethane to give benzyl alkyl ether, alkyl benzoate, benzyl ester, α, β -unsaturated aldehyde, benzaldehyde and a small quantity of benzyl alcohol. *p*-Nitrobenzaldehyde and *n*-butyl acetal gave only *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and a trace of *p*-nitrobenzyl alcohol. The mechanism of the formation of benzyl alkyl ether is explained by a hydride ion transfer and that of α, β -unsaturated aldehyde by an aldol type of condensation. The aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes produced in the reaction could undergo Tischenko reaction in the presence of antimony or iron alkoxides to give the esters.

STUDIES on the action of Lewis acids on acetals^{1,2} reveal that the Lewis acids which can expand their coordination number bring about the rearrangement of acetals. Antimony pentachloride³ and ferric chloride⁴ can expand their coordination number beyond five and three, respectively. Therefore, these Lewis acids may also be expected to bring about the rearrangement of acetals. Extensive literature survey indicates that no work has been reported on the action of antimony pentachloride and ferric chloride on aromatic acetals. We report herein the products formed in the above reaction and discuss the mechanism of their formation.

Experimental

Moisture was rigorously excluded throughout the experimental manipulations. The commercially available antimony pentachloride (Koch-Light) purified by vacuum distillation (68°/14 mm)⁵ and iron (III) chloride (B.D.H.) kept in a vacuum oven containing potassium hydroxide were used as such.

To a stirred solution of the acetal (0.2 mol) in dry 1,2-dichloroethane (75 ml) was added gradually antimony pentachloride (0.05 mol) in dry 1,2-dichloroethane at room temperature (30°) during 30 min. The dark green complex was treated with ice-cold water. The organic layer was separated, washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4).

In case of ferric chloride, 16 g (0.1 mol) of it was added to a stirred solution of the acetal (0.2 mol) in dry 1,2-dichloroethane (150 ml) and the reaction was continued for 1 h at room temperature (30°). The dark red-brown reaction mixture was processed as above.

The products (Table 1) were separated by tlc and characterised on the basis of their spectral

(ir and pmr) data and co-glc with authentic samples (Toshniwal, SE30 column-FID- N_2 carrier gas).

Results and Discussion

Formation of benzyl alkyl ether: Alkoxides of aluminium^{6,7}, titanium⁸ and tin² are known to have been used for the reduction of aldehydes by hydride transfer mechanism. Therefore, alkoxides of antimony and iron produced *in situ* might be responsible for the reduction of the intermediate carbonium ion by a Meerwein-Ponndorf-Vereley reduction with a hydride ion transfer. Infact, the yield of the ether increased when the alkoxide of antimony pentachloride was used directly instead of antimony pentachloride.

The first step in this mechanism could be the formation of an arylalkoxy complex⁹

which may decompose under the reaction conditions to give a carbonium ion and a complex anion,

The complex anion may react with another molecule of $SbCl_5$ to give the alkoxide $SbCl_4OR$,

The alkoxide could serve as the source of hydride ion required for a MPV type of reduction.

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

A similar mechanism may be proposed for the action of ferric chloride on aromatic acetals.

Formation of α,β -unsaturated aldehyde: The use of Lewis acids like TiCl_4 and its alkoxides as a base for an aldol condensation, has been reported in the literature⁶. Therefore, the aliphatic aldehyde can condense with benzaldehyde in the presence of the base, the complex anion or the alkoxide to form an α,β -unsaturated aldehyde via Claisen-Schmidt reaction.

where, $\text{R}' = \text{H}, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, \text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$,

The efficiency of antimony alkoxides and ferric alkoxides in bringing about the condensation in the present study was found to be enhanced when the Lewis acid to acetal ratio was 1 : 4 as compared with the ratio 1 : 1 or 2 : 1. The reason might be the absence of free SbCl_5 or FeCl_3 when the

catalyst concentration was only half that of the acetal resulting in the conversion of all the Lewis acid into the alkoxide. This would have increased the basic alkoxide species in the medium.

p-Nitrobenzaldehyde di-*n*-butyl acetal gave only *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde. This may be due to the instability of the incipient carbonium ion necessary for the formation of benzyl alkyl ether (Scheme 1) or the ester (Schemes 2 and 3).

R^+ may eliminate a proton to form an olefin.

A small quantity of *p*-nitrobenzyl alcohol might have been formed by a M-P-V type of reduction of the aldehyde as stated before. However, *p*-methylbenzaldehyde di-*n*-butyl acetal gave an increased yield of the ether. This may be attributed to the higher stability of the carbonium ion brought about by the electron releasing, stabilising influence of the methyl group.

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